

Technical Marvels, Part 6: Musical Automaton

Historic music machines are among the most magnificent automatons. They delighted visitors to fairgrounds, played in inns and railroad stations and entertained passengers on huge ocean liners. Many devices are still fully functional today. They range from tiny singing birds, music boxes, barrel organs, flute-playing clocks and mechanical violins to self-playing pianos and huge organs. A short journey back in time to the world of analog music. Music automatons have survived in numerous museums.

By Herbert Bruderer

The most famous musical automaton figures can be found in Paris and Neuchâtel (Switzerland). Peter Kintzing created his dulcimer player (see Fig. 1) in collaboration with David Roentgen.

Fig. 1: Dulcimer player (1784). The dulcimer player by Peter Kintzing uses tiny hammers for the dulcimer. She moves her head and eyes, but not her upper body. The control mechanism is not located in the automaton figure, but underneath it. (Credit: Musée des arts et métiers/Cnam, Paris, image: Pascal Faligot).

The three Jaquet-Droz automated figures, including the musician (see Fig. 2), are regularly presented to the public in Neuchâtel (Switzerland).

Fig. 2: Musician (1774). The automaton figure built by Henri-Louis Jaquet-Droz operates the keys of the flute-playing organ with her fingers. She plays five pieces of music, which were probably composed by the clockmaker himself (Credit: Musée d'art et d'histoire, Neuchâtel).

The Swiss clockmakers Pierre Jaquet-Droz and Henri-Louis Jaquet-Droz are regarded as the inventors of the singing bird (see Fig. 3).

Fig. 3: Automated singing birds (1780). Precision mechanical singing birds once adorned many snuff boxes. (Credit: Reuge SA, Sainte-Croix VD).

Mechanical singing birds in cages were particularly popular (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4: Songbird in cage automaton, made by Blaise Bontems, Paris, France, circa 1900–1910. After winding the object is operated from a lever on the side of the base. “The bird sings, opening and closing its beak and moving its head from side to side as its tail also rises and falls”, Science Museum Group, London (Credit: The Board of Trustees of the Science Museum).

Music boxes (see Figs. 5–7) were widespread.

Fig. 5: Mechanical singing bird box, Geneva, Switzerland, circa 1820. “When wound up, the bird turns and flutters its wings while music plays. These singing bird boxes were especially popular in the East” (Credit: Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York).

Fig. 6: The tambour timbres vue cylinder-operated music box, with a selection of eight melodies (Sainte-Croix VD, around 1895). The bells and drum enhance the range of sounds (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

Fig. 7: The Voix céleste cylinder-operated music box. The music box has swing-through tongues. This section shows the brass cylinders and the two sound combs. The Geneva clockmaker Antoine Favre invented the steel rib in 1796 (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

Disc musical boxes (see Fig. 8) are easier to manufacture than cylinder music boxes.

Fig. 8: The Edelweiss disc-type music box. This device from the Thorens company (Sainte-Croix VD) is equipped with a coin slot. The sound recording medium is a steel plate (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

Barrel organs (see Fig. 9) still enliven streets and squares today.

Fig 9: Barrel organ (1991) by Franz Oehrlein, barrel organ and automaton maker from Mainz, Germany (Credit Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

Many mechanical musicians (see Fig. 10) are still in working order.

Fig. 10: Automaton figure, clown, Vichy, Paris, circa 1878 (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

The Hupfeld violins (see Fig. 11) were considered a technical marvel.

Fig. 11: Phonoliszt violin (1908). The pneumatic self-playing violin made by Ludwig Hupfeld AG, Leipzig, consists of a piano and three violins. The Hupfeld violin is controlled by a perforated paper roll. (Credit: Technisches Museum Wien).

On the Britannic, the sister ship of the “unsinkable” Titanic, there was a huge philharmonic organ. (see Figs. 12–14). The organ, which was lost for a long time, is now in Seewen in Switzerland.

Fig. 12: Welte philharmonic organ on the Britannic, the sister ship of the Titanic (Wikimedia commons).

Fig. 13: Welte philharmonic organ with console, M. Welte & Söhne, Freiburg im Breisgau, manufactured in 1913/14 for the luxury liner “Britannic”, extended in 1937 (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

Fig. 14: Welte philharmonic organ, 1942 organ pipes (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

The Mortier organs (see Fig. 15) are also quite impressive.

Fig. 15: Mortier organ (around 1915). This Belgian dance organ (factory no. 1010) was made by Theophile Mortier, Antwerp (Credit: Museum für Musikautomaten, Seewen SO).

This post is the sixth in a series that presents selected technical marvels from the fields of computing technology, mathematics, astronomy, surveying, time measurement, looms, and automatons (automaton figures, chess-playing machines, musical automatons, automaton writers, drawing automatons, automaton clocks, picture clocks, globes, and historical robots). The examples are largely

from the 15th to 20th centuries and do not claim to be exhaustive. In particular, artifacts are included for which high-quality illustrations are available. Most of the objects come from Europe, with a few from Africa, America, Asia, and Australia. The order is predominantly chronological. Famous names such as Archimedes, Hipparchus, Heron of Alexandria, Leonardo da Vinci, Galileo Galilei, John Napier, Jost Bürgi, Blaise Pascal, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, and Charles Babbage are associated with these works. In some cases, however, the inventors are unknown (e.g. abacus, Antikythera Mechanism, yupana, quipu); see [Technical Marvels, Part 5: Chess Automats – Communications of the ACM](#)

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References

This paper is based on:

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